
A Study of Well Being of Teacher Trainees in Relation to Their Social Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Well-being in psychology is a new area of research. Progress of any nation depends largely on well-being of its citizens. All the intellectual, creative, educational and socio-cultural advancements are possible if the individuals of the nation possess physical, mental, social, emotional and spiritual well-being. Similarly teacher trainee's efficiency and effectiveness largely depend upon their all-round well-being. The present study was an attempt to study the relationship between well-being and social intelligence among teacher trainees.

Introduction-

Our wellbeing is shaped by genes our upbringing, personal circumstances and choices and social conditions which we live. Collective wellbeing is improved if we live in a peaceful and flourishing society. Feeling of wellbeing are fundamental to the overall health of an individual enabling them to successfully overcome difficulties and achieve whatever they want out of life. Past experiences, attitude and outlook can all impact well-being as can physical or emotional trauma following specific incidents. Children with learning and developmental disorders may experience considerably more stress than typically developing children and this impact both their health and wellbeing. It is the state of being contented, healthy, and successful. In the process of making him socialized the family, the school, neighbourhood, culture, peer group and many other interacting factors play their significant roles. But parents encouragement is of great significant in developing social values and social intelligence among their children.

Well-being-

Well-being requires harmony between mind and body. It implies a sense of balance and ease with the pressure in a person's life. There is no under stimulation and no excessive negative stress; above all there is a sense of control over one's destiny. Well-being is concerned with how and why people experience their lives in positive ways including cognitive and affect reactions. Generally, well-being may be characterized as the subjective feeling of contentment, happiness and satisfaction or worry. Different people viewed well-being in different perspectives. Some considered it as a balance and integration of oneself and some as a quest for maximum human functioning of body, mind and spirit. Positive psychological definitions of well-being generally include some of five general characteristics

- The active pursuit of well-being
- The balance of attributes.
- Positive effect or life satisfaction
- Pre-social behaviour
- Multiple dimensions

Social Intelligence-

Social intelligence is quite important for a person to be successful in life. Many people may have a higher abstract intelligence, but they are miserable failures in life situations on account of the deficiency in this type of intelligence, however usually abstract and social intelligence go side by side. The word social intelligence is derived from two words –social and intelligence. Social refers to the modern society which is very complex where intellectual competence has become more and more sophisticated and this competence is social intelligence and can be defined as intelligence that lies behind the group interaction and behaviour. The concept of social intelligence was first proposed by Thorndike (1920) in an article in Harper's magazine. He said that social intelligence in the form of inter-personal effectiveness was of vital importance for the success in many fields. "The best mechanic in a factory", he wrote "may fail as a foreman for lack of social intelligence"

Need and justification of the study-

Today's world is a world of challenges. It is full of tensions, anxieties and frustration. The top most responsibility of the world is on the shoulder of teachers, but we can fulfil his responsibility with great care when he is free from all tensions and worries. If the teacher is full of aggression he will never listen to

their students properly and it will adversely affect the relationship of teacher and student. So, the teacher must be mentally strong. For it, is necessary that his wellbeing should be good. Aminpoor (2013) found a positive relationship between social intelligence and happiness among college students. Prathima and Kulsum (2013) also showed that there was a significant relationship between secondary school teachers' social intelligence and their mental health. The significant difference exists between male and female secondary school teachers' mental health..

Shrama (2019) found a positive correlation between social intelligence and well being of teenagers. It is an established fact that the performance of a teacher mainly depends upon his being psychological state of mind. Hassaniraad, Khodayarifard and Hejazi, (2021) examined the effectiveness of character strengths training program on well-being. They decided to reinforce the character strengths of students to improve mental well-being. Pre-test and post- test design was adopted in the study. 34 students (15 participants were in experimental group and 19 were in control group) studying in Teharn university were selected.. Findings reveal effective role of character strengths in improving well-being.

This investigation is undertaken to the study well being in relation to social intelligence. Both are inextricably linked together. Social intelligence has an evitable role to play in the development of well being among teacher trainees and helping them in achieving new horizons of success.

Hypotheses of the Study-

1. There exist significance relationships between well-being social intelligence among teacher trainees.
2. There exists significance between well-being among teacher trainees of rural and urban areas.
3. There exists a significance difference between social intelligence of teacher trainees of rural and urban areas.

Method and Sample -

The present study was undertaken to study the well-being among teacher trainees in relation to social intelligence. Descriptive Survey method was employed to conduct the present study. Co-relational approach was adopted to ascertain the relationship between well being and social intelligence of teacher trainees. For the present study, the sample was selected from different colleges of Ludhiana district. The sample consisted of 200 teacher trainees (100 rural and 100 urban) selected from the colleges of education of Ludhiana district, Punjab. Data was collected by using PGI General Wellbeing Measure by Verma and Verma and Social intelligence Scale (SIS) by Chaddha and Ganeshan .

Results and Interpretation –

The data was analysed by using Statistical techniques like Pearson's product moment correlation and t-test.

Figure :1

Showing Coefficient of Correlation between Well-being and Social Intelligence among Teacher trainees (N=200)

As a significant relationship was found between well-being and social intelligence among teacher trainees, therefore Hypothesis 1 stating, “There exists a significant relationship between well-being and social intelligence among teacher trainees” stands accepted.

Figure : 2

Bar Graph showing Difference between Mean Scores of Well-being among Teacher Trainees of Rural and Urban areas (N=200)

Fig. 4.6 also indicates that teacher trainees of rural and urban areas experience different levels of well-being. As mean score of teacher trainees of rural areas on the variable of well-being was found to be higher than of teacher trainees of urban areas, it may further be concluded that teacher trainees of rural areas experience higher level of well-being as compared to their urban counterparts

Figure : 3

Bar Graph showing Difference between Mean Scores of Social Intelligence among Teacher Trainees of Rural and Urban areas (N=200)

Fig. 3 also indicates that teacher trainees of rural and urban areas experience same type of social intelligence with no difference in social intelligence for teacher trainees of rural and urban areas.

Discussion and Conclusions-

A significant difference was found between mean scores of well-being of teacher trainees of rural and urban areas. This indicates that teacher trainees of rural and urban areas experience different level of well-being. As mean score of teacher trainees of urban areas on the variable of well-being was found to be higher than of adolescent boys, it may further be concluded that teacher trainees of urban areas exhibit higher level of well-being as compared to their male counterparts.

The findings of present study are important for the improvement in the quality of education,. Social Intelligence is also an ability which plays a major role in life. Educators and administrators should bring about an awareness among teacher trainees to give more importance to well being.

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